

GENDER INEQUALITY IN SOCIETY*Dr. Reni Francis**Rumana Shaikh I/C Principal**Ms. Arusha Siddique and Ms.**Student Teachers**MES's Pillai College of Education and Research, Chembur***Abstract**

Gender Inequality is basically in the mind. The status of women in complex society like India isn't uniform. Inequality has been an issue for many years and there have been many ideas and problems surrounding it. Even after all of these years, women are still not being treated the same as men, regardless of their education or professionalism. The present study focus on how women are treated and portrayed in our society. The research shows awareness towards gender Inequality. We focus on four areas to explain how women are portrayed in the society.

Objective:-

: To highlight discrimination on the basis of gender.

Introduction:-

- : Role of women in family.
- : Role of women in workplace.
- : Role of women in Bollywood.
- : Role of women in Advertisement.

Role of women in family:-

In society when the girl child is born she is considered inauspicious whereas the birth of boy is a cause for celebration. It is a harsh reality that even today. Some people see girl child as a burden. The important decisions are taken by the male and the females have no or little say in it. Even today girls are being told to come home before 9pm, they are being told to dress according to their parents and the boys have every rights to wear whatever they want. All the house hold chores, rearing the child etc. are expected to be done by the women.

Role of women in workplace:-

In the work place the men usually hold the higher position and the women often hold lower paid positions such as secretaries. It is something which still exists in the work place today. An obstacle that many women face in the workplace is sexual harassment. While the #MeToo movement has helped to shed light on the issue, little had been known, until now about how many women subjected to this type of mistreatment. A survey conducted in January 2018 by the nonprofit **Stop Street Harassment** found 38% of women have experienced sexual harassment in the workplace, and 81% reported experience some form of sexual harassment in their lifetime, including verbal or physical assault. Despite being more educated than men above all this unequal pay is the major inequality faced by women at workplace.

Role of women in Bollywood:-

“No one can guarantee the success of a film, so why discrimination?” this was once said by Kangana Ranaut in an interview with NDTV. The gender pay gap extends even to Bollywood. According to the world economic forum, there is no country on earth where women make as much as men for the same work. Even top actresses struggle just to get what they deserve. Once Aditi Roy Hydari said in an interview that “I don't really understand why we are paid less than the male actors because we put equal efforts”. In 2003, leading filmmaker Karan Johar dropped a list actress Kareena Kapoor for KAL HO NA HO for asking as much money as the lead actor Shahrukh

Khan. Preity Zinta ended up with the role. In 2015, after starting in hits such as QUEEN and TANU WEDS MANU RETURNS, Kangana Ranaut told to NDTV she deserves to get paid as much as actors. In an interview with glamour, Priyanka Chopra who also headlines ABC's Quantico and starred in boy watch, said "I was told that female actors are replaceable in films because they just stand behind a guy any way. We're told were too provocative are that or that being sexy is our strength, which it can be, and it is, but that is not the only thing we have". Male lead films earn more than female lead films. **Eg:** Singham and Mardani. "When women centered films become hits then the disparity will end". Said Priyanka Chopra. Though female lead films doing well at the box office but were still very far from pay and budget parity.

Role of women in Advertisement:-

Gender has an important role to play in modern advertising. It describes not only the socially constructed disparity between men and women, but also the stereotypes of masculinity and femininity. Let's take an example of bathing soap for advertising like Lux, Dove, etc. they show women actors to roll around in flower petals for you or lying in the bath tub, but for a soap like Dettol they show a boy child or a man. Another example is when we see the advertisement of sport bikes, they are mostly male centered.

Conclusion:-

This bias has to be removed. Both males and females are equally capable of doing things. If the nation is to progress, gender inequality must be brought in to effect. Equality does not imply that women can behave in any manner they see fit, but it means that people of both the sexes get equal opportunities. The major reason that we are still facing the gender inequality is not educating girl child and lack of awareness about gender equality. As the teacher it is our responsibility to promote gender equality not only in the class room, but also in the society. I would like to conclude this paper with quote given by Malala Yousafzai "we cannot all succeed when half of us are hold back".